

**BIOECOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF TREES AND SHRUBS INTRODUCED IN
JIZAKH CITY**

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Abstract. This article discusses the bioecological characteristics of introduced trees and shrubs in the city of Jizzakh, their adaptation to the urban ecological environment, and the results of monitoring. The climate resistance, growth rate, decorativeness, and ecological significance of the introduced plants were analyzed.

Keywords: introduction, bioecological characteristics, monitoring, trees and shrubs, urbanization, green areas, ecology, adaptation, Jizzakh city.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются биоэкологические характеристики интродуцированных деревьев и кустарников в городе Джизак, их адаптация к городской экологической среде и результаты мониторинга. Проанализированы климатоустойчивость, темпы роста, декоративность и экологическая значимость интродуцированных растений.

Ключевые слова: интродукция, биоэкологические характеристики, мониторинг, деревья и кустарники, урбанизация, зеленые зоны, экология, адаптация, город Джизак.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Jizzax shahrida introduksiya qilingan daraxt va buta o‘simliklarining bioekologik xususiyatlari, ularning shahar ekologik muhitiga moslashuvi hamda monitoring natijalari yoritilgan. Introduksiya qilingan o‘simliklarning iqlimga chidamliligi, o‘shish sur‘ati, dekorativligi va ekologik ahamiyati tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so‘zlar: introduksiya, bioekologik xususiyat, monitoring, daraxt-butalar, urbanizatsiya, yashil hudud, ekologiya, moslashuvchanlik, Jizzax shahri.

Nowadays, the importance of trees and shrubs in improving the ecological environment of the city, purifying atmospheric air and creating a favorable microclimate in residential areas is extremely great. Especially in areas where urbanization processes are intensifying, expanding green spaces is considered one of the urgent environmental tasks. Therefore, the use of ornamental, fast-growing and environmentally resistant trees and shrubs introduced from different parts of the world has been widely established.

The city of Jizzakh has a sharply continental climate, with high temperatures in the summer months and cold weather in the winter. In such climatic conditions, not all plant species can develop equally. Therefore, studying the bioecological characteristics of introduced trees and shrubs, determining the degree of their adaptation, and conducting regular monitoring are of great scientific and practical importance.

Introduced plants have a positive effect on the ecology of the city. They absorb dust and harmful gases in the air, produce oxygen, reduce wind speed and create an aesthetic landscape. Some species are also of great importance in preventing soil erosion. They are also widely used in the improvement of city streets, avenues and parks due to their decorative properties. In recent years, the number of introduced trees and shrubs has been increasing in the city of Jizzakh. In particular, such tree species as chestnut, catalpa, magnolia, cypress, camellia, virgin juniper, Japanese sophora, gledichia, as well as various ornamental shrubs are being planted. While some of these plants are well adapted to the local climate, some species are sensitive to high

temperatures or moisture deficiency. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct monitoring work on their biological development, growing season, resistance to diseases and pests.

Bioecological monitoring is an important method for assessing the status of introduced plants. During monitoring, indicators such as tree height, trunk diameter, leafing period, flowering and fruiting period, and drought resistance are determined. Based on the data obtained, the ecological stability of plants and promising species are assessed.

Among the introduced trees and shrubs in the city of Jizzakh, fast-growing and decorative species are of particular importance. Many of them are resistant to atmospheric pollution in urban conditions and play an important role in expanding green areas. In particular, trees such as plane, catalpa, gledichia and sophora are distinguished by their high ecological adaptability. The bioecological characteristics of introduced trees are primarily determined by their adaptation to climatic conditions. In the city of Jizzakh, the air temperature rises to +40°C in the summer months and the lack of precipitation creates the need to select drought-resistant species. In this regard, gledichia and Japanese sophora tolerate high temperatures well. These species have a strong root system and are able to absorb moisture from deep layers of the soil.

The catalpa tree is important as a fast-growing and ornamental species. Its broad leaves help trap dust particles in the air. In addition, the catalpa creates an aesthetic landscape during its flowering period. However, this species is sensitive to severe frosts, and in some years its branches are partially damaged.

Cypress and camellia trees are evergreen plants that retain their decorative appearance throughout the year. They have the ability to absorb harmful gases in urban air. These trees are of great ecological importance, especially in areas with a lot of car traffic.

Among the introduced shrubs, barberry, ligustrum, jasmine and rose species are widespread. These shrubs are planted more for ornamental purposes. Some species are also useful in strengthening the soil and reducing erosion.

During the monitoring work, the phenological phases of trees and shrubs were observed. The period of leaf growth in the spring, vegetative development in the summer, and leaf fall in the fall were studied. As a result of the observations, it was determined that the growing season of most introduced trees was adapted to local climatic conditions. In some tropical and subtropical species, cases of late onset of vegetation or damage from frost in winter were noted. The impact of diseases and pests was also studied during the monitoring process. Fungal diseases, leaf spot and spider mites were observed in some trees. Such conditions negatively affect the decorativeness and growth rate of plants. Therefore, regular phytosanitary control is necessary.

The ecological efficiency of introduced trees and shrubs was also highly appreciated. They reduce the amount of carbon dioxide in the air, release oxygen, and soften the urban microclimate. The expansion of green areas also has a positive effect on the health of the city's population.

In the city of Jizzakh, introduced trees and shrubs were found to be of great importance in improving the ecological environment in conditions of urbanization. Studies have shown that many introduced tree species have successfully adapted to local climatic conditions and have high decorative and ecological efficiency. In particular, trees such as gledichia, Japanese sophora, cypress, and catalpa are distinguished by their drought resistance and air-purifying properties.

The monitoring results showed the need for regular monitoring of the condition of introduced plants. Reducing the impact of diseases and pests, improving the irrigation system, and properly organizing agrotechnical measures will ensure the long-term survival of introduced plants.

In the future, it is advisable to use environmentally sustainable, drought-resistant and decorative trees and shrubs in the expansion of green areas of the city of Jizzakh. In-depth study

of the bioecological characteristics of introduced plants will serve as an important scientific basis for improving the ecology of the city and preserving biodiversity.

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